
SYSTEM MODELLING AND CONTROL OF A QUADCOPTER WITH ENERGY EFFICIENT ELECTRIC PROPULSION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

The continuous growth in flight operations has led to public concern regarding the impact of aviation emission on climate change. There is also a need for technological advancements in extending drone technology to places where humans can't reach such as calamity struck areas and to help deliver medicines in rural regions. Combining these two ideas have propelled to simulate a drone model and battery modelling. Although several papers are limited to either of the models, this paper aims to develop a drone model capable of electric propulsion and a battery model to power the electric need. By providing the concept of integrating two novel ideas, lay a platform to a new research potential of further studies. The proposed drone model is made modular to be applicable for an aircraft and the battery model to propel any carrier by increasing the battery packs. A, it is necessary to identify individual contribution from each power source and optimise each system for the overall performance. The designed power management strategy will effectively direct the power flow between power sources to satisfy the load demand in each flight phase. The novelty to the study comes by combining all three models and letting them operate co-dependently whose modularity also contributes to its singularity. The integrated system model will be used to perform several static and dynamic ground tests both on simulation later confirmed by experiment. The various system level test data will be collected and analysed. Also, the collected experimental test results will be compared with the simulation results to provide further suggestions and improvements to power distribution strategy and overall propulsion system.

Keywords: Quadcopter simulation, Battery-modelling, Motor-modelling, SOC estimation, variable load modelling, battery and motor simulation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study talks about modelling a quadcopter and a suitable controller in order to control it. The study extends to generation of the trajectory and the copter following the said path (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011). MATLAB is used for modelling the quadcopter and its controller. SIMULINK is used to perform a battery modelling along with the motor model for the quadcopter (Huria et al, 2012). There is a plethora of technology available for modelling the copter and its controller (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011). There are means to model the battery and to model the motor

(Waltermann, 1996). But there are several studies conducted to model all three together which are interdependent. There are technologies and facilities that are available to do this hence this it concentrates on modelling all three together and analysing their performance during flight. In this study the robotics toolbox is used to model the quadcopter and to develop the collision avoidance system block.

1.1. Identifying the problem

As the technology improves and industrialization progresses there is a threat on the fossil fuels and

the amount of greenhouse emission that is being expelled out into the atmosphere. Hence there is a need for a clean energy resource and electric propulsion is the way to go with zero greenhouse emission and zero noise pollution. During any calamities that puts life in danger sending another person to the site might be a threat to life hence using drones are a much safer option (Câmara, 2014). Doctors aren't always able to visit always and everywhere but a drone can. If the drone is smart enough to navigate on its own by knowing just the starting and the ending position, then this could help provide health care much faster and better. The drone should also be capable of avoiding any obstacles on its way. It should be able to relay its battery charge left to ascertain if it can complete the mission or not.

1.2. Motivation

Providing a solution to the above stated problems from the foundation of motivation to the study conducted. In order to support the electric propulsion a battery model is developed. The model is designed in such a way that it is modular enough to be used even on a fixed wing drone. The same model can be used in packs and connected in series or parallel to power a fixed wing aircraft. The quadcopter is made smarter by designing a robust controller. The controller is equipped with the capacity to generate an optimal trajectory given the starting and the ending positions and certain waypoints in between. It is also equipped with collision avoidance system in order to prevent any collision. On the whole the designed quadcopter is smart enough to generate trajectory and avoid collision and relay the charge remaining (by calculating SOC). The main aim of the study is to build a quadcopter with such specification and analyse its performance in flight.

1.3. Limitations

The study is limited to the analysis being linear in nature. All the nonlinear in the problem are linearized as a linear equation is used to obtain the solution to the problem. The payload that the quadcopter can carry is also limited to 2Kg. If the payload increases, then the load on the battery

increases and hence the total time that the battery can power the copter will reduce. The paper doesn't confirm any collision avoidance checks although the controller is capable of it. In spite of the above limitations the study has been made and the simulations so programmed to mimic the real world in the closest way possible.

1.4. Outline

Firstly, the study is divided into two main parts, the low-level control and the high-level control. The high-level control deals with the modelling of the quadcopter its controller, trajectory generation and following the trajectory. The low-level control talks about the underlying system of battery modelling which powers the entire system and the motor modelling which provides the necessary thrust (Huria et al, 2012). Following the quadcopter modelling the waypoints given as input are used to generate the trajectory for the quadcopter. The variable loading conditions from the MATLAB simulation is used as an input to the motor model. This then draws an appropriate power from the battery. Kalman filter algorithm is used to measure the SOC of the battery and is given as a feedback to the controller to determine how long the copter can stay flight.

1. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE SYSTEM

This paper talks about the development of quadcopter and controller system model and its controlling. For a stable control of the quadcopter selection and development of a relevant controller is vital. Here, a PD controller is being used as the problem is linearized and assumes an ideal condition. The system model for the controller is written in MATLAB and the same is run for simulation validation. Once the simulation is positively validated the same inputs are given to the actual quadcopter and the results are compared. Equations of motion plays an important role in modelling the quadcopter.

1.1 Equation of motion

Figure 1: Frames of reference

As shown in figure 1 above, A represents the inertial frame of reference and B represents the body frame of reference. Ψ represents the rotation in z-axis, ϕ in y-axis and θ in x-axis, each corresponding to yaw, roll and pitch respectively.

A transformation matrix is formulated in order to correlate inertial frame of reference and body frame of reference. This ensures that the control inputs that are given to the inertial frame of reference is similar in the body frame of reference. All the vectors of both the frames of reference are parallel to the axis. Vector p in A is given by equation 1.

$$p = \sum_i A p_i a_i \quad (1)$$

And vector in B is given by equation 2,

$$p = \sum_i B p_i b_i \quad (2)$$

The vectors are then rotated, ${}^A R_B$ and translated, ${}^A T_B$ to obtain the final vector in the reference frame.

$$A_p = {}^A R_B B_p + {}^A T_B \quad (3)$$

Adding angular velocity term to the above equation, the below equation is obtained.

$$\frac{d}{dt} b_i = \omega * b_i \quad (4)$$

The angular velocity in equation 4 is independent of the co-ordinate system and produces the same effect in any axis. The angular velocity in the vector form is given by

$$\omega = (p + q + r) \cdot b_i \quad (5)$$

Euler X-Y-Z transformation is performed starting from the inertial frame of reference, with a yaw (ψ) followed by roll (ϕ) and pitch (θ) to arrive at the body frame of reference. The resulting rotation matrix is as given below in equation 6.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi)\cos(\theta) - \sin(\phi)\sin(\psi)\sin(\theta) & -\cos(\phi)\sin(\psi) & \cos(\psi)\sin(\theta) + \cos(\theta)\sin(\phi)\sin(\psi) \\ \cos(\theta)\sin(\psi) + \cos(\psi)\sin(\phi)\sin(\theta) & \cos(\phi)\cos(\psi) & \sin(\psi)\sin(\theta) - \cos(\psi)\cos(\theta)\sin(\phi) \\ -\cos(\phi)\sin(\theta) & \sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi)\cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

1.2 Motor Model

This study makes use of four DC motors to provide the relevant thrust to the quadcopter. The motor specifications are as given the table 1.

Armature Voltage	240V
Field Voltage	300V
Power	5HP ~ 20HP
Speed	0~1750 rpm

Table 1: DC Motor Specifications

A DC motor with the same specifications is modelled in SIMULINK and is powered by the modelled battery. This constitutes of the low-level control, whose output in linked to the high-level control in MATLAB. The motor model developed in SIMULINK is also considered in MATLAB. The mathematical model for the same is as given below (McDonald, 2012).

Each motor has an angular velocity which is represented by ω_i where I represent the motor number as, ω_1 , ω_2 , ω_3 and ω_4 respectively. It is evident that each motor provides a specific thrust which when combined acts as the force or lift to the quadcopter. This is mathematically represented by equation (7) below.

$$F_i = K_f * \omega_i^2 \quad (7)$$

Where,

F_i is the force from each motor

K_f is a constant

ω_i is the angular velocity of each motor

The value of K_f is determined experimentally and is found to be $6.11 * 10^{-8} \text{ N/rpm}^2$

Each motor also provides a specific moment which is given by equation 8 as below.

$$M_i = K_m * \omega_i^2 \quad (8)$$

Where,

M_i is the force from each motor

K_m is a constant

ω_i is the angular velocity of each motor

The value of K_m is determined experimentally and is found to be $1.5 * 10^{-9} \text{ Nm/rpm}^2$

When the motor is modelled, it is expected to have an error which is fed as the feedback for error correction. It is important to model this error between the desired motor speed and the actual motor speed for stable control of the system. The control command (desired motor speed) given to the motor is related to the actual motor speed is given by equation 9 as given below.

$$\dot{\omega}_i = k_1 * (\omega_i^{des} - \omega_i) \quad (9)$$

Where,

$\dot{\omega}_i$ is the feedback after computing the error of each motor

k_1 is the motor gain which is determined experimentally to satisfy the control stability

ω_i^{des} is the desired rotor speed of each motor

ω_i is the actual rotor speed of each motor

After experimentation, motor gain, k_1 is approximately found to be 20 s^{-1} . This value of gain gave a much better approximation of the simulation to the real case system.

An alternative approach to this would be to directly command the thrust and the torque values to the motor. Bearing in mind, that each value is within the range of its maxima and minima. In

addition to this, a separate algorithm has to be generated to convert the torque and thrust values into motor commands to the quadcopter during its actual flight.

1.3 Rigid body Dynamics

The angular moment of the quadcopter is given by the below expression: (Featherstone, 2014)

$$L = I * \omega \quad (10)$$

If the total moment is given by M, then equation 10 can be written as given below

$$\dot{L} = M \quad (11)$$

Equation 11 is true in the inertial frame of reference but gets complicated as the altitude of the quadcopter changes. As the altitude changes, the moment of inertia tensor, I, also changes and hence is a function of time and hence is non-diagonal in nature. This is difficult to model and also consumes huge simulation power. Hence to simplify the problem the equation is expressed in the body frame of reference. The body frame is aligned with the principle axis the moment of inertia tensor is diagonal, as it remains a constant. However, the vectors in the body frame of reference, b_i , are time dependent, hence a time derivative of the angular moment equation is required which is given by the equation below.

$$\dot{L} = \sum_i^B \dot{L}_i b_i + \sum_i^B L_i \dot{b}_i \quad (12)$$

We know that, $\dot{b} = \omega * b$

Therefore,

$$\dot{L} = \sum_i^B \dot{L}_i b_i + \sum_i \omega * {}^B L_i \quad (13)$$

$$\sum {}^B L_i b_i = L$$

$$\dot{L} = \sum_i^B \dot{L}_i b_i + \omega L \quad (14)$$

Considering that moment of inertia is constant in body frame of reference, Euler's equation is given by the below equation.

$$I^B \dot{\omega} = {}^B M - {}^B \omega \times I^B \omega \quad (15)$$

Each motor produces a force, F_i and is placed at a distance l from the centre of mass. Hence this also means that the motors can exert some torque on the body and produces a moment M_i perpendicular to the plane of rotation of the blade. While a set of diagonal rotors rotate in clockwise direction the other set of diagonal rotors rotate in anti-clockwise direction. From this it can be said that M_1 and M_3 act in the positive direction while M_2 and M_4 act in the negative direction in the body frame of reference. However, all the forces $\sum F_i$ act in the positive z direction to produce thrust to lift upwards. Based on the above explained theory the angular velocity, ω in the body frame of reference can be expressed in terms of p , q and r as given below. This is obtained by combining equation 3 and 15.

The net yaw ψ , in b_3 axis is given by the summation of motor's torques, M_i

Where $\gamma = \frac{K_M}{K_F}$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & l & 0 & -l \\ -l & 0 & l & 0 \\ \gamma & -\gamma & \gamma & -\gamma \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \\ F_4 \end{bmatrix} = u_2 \quad (16)$$

Where u_2 is the second set of inputs.

Therefore,

$$m\ddot{r} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -mg \end{bmatrix} + R \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ u_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$I * \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p} \\ \dot{q} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} = u_2 - \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} * I \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Equation 17 is in inertial frame of reference and equation 18 is in body frame of reference. u_1 and u_2 are the two sets of control inputs given by the controller to the motor. u_1 refers to the thrusting control input while u_2 refers to the moment or torque input to the motor. Together, it lifts the quadcopter up and also keeps it stabilized by providing appropriate u_2 input.

The controller makes sure that right commands are given so that the quadcopter follows the desired path. The desired or the required trajectory is fed to the system in the form of waypoints. The quadcopter module is also expected to relay the current position to the controller (Kreciglowa et al., 2017). Based on the current position acquired and the next position taken from the input given, the controller gives an appropriate thrust, torque, moment and yaw angle commands. This control signal is then relayed on to the quadcopter a motor command which takes the quadcopter to the next desired position from the current position. Once the next position is reached the feedback system sends an error feedback to the controller. This feedback error is the difference between the current and the desired position (Guerrero-Bonilla et al, 2017). If both are the current and the positions are the same, then the error is calculated to be zero. If the two positions are different, based on whether the quadcopter has overshoot or undershot the desired position the error will be positive or negative, respectively. It is a simulation and the quadcopter are expected to go to each specific waypoint and not over or undershoot the specified waypoints (Watterson et al, 2016).

To achieve this the control law is so selected that the entire path between any two waypoints is divided into two parts. The first part where the quadcopter accelerates and the second part where it starts to decelerate. This is done so that once it starts decelerating, it will come to a stop at the exact position of the input waypoint and does not overshoot or undershoot it. Although this does not happen in the real case scenario, it serves as a good approximation of the reality and best imitates the real conditions as similar results are obtained.

The entire flight path I of three different types with respect to signals sent from the controller. Firstly, the climb followed by hovering or cruising followed by landing or decent. During the climbing phase, the controller sends a series of positive thrust and torque signals to the motor. In addition to this, an appropriate yaw angle is given as an input based on the rate of climb, angle of climb and the requirement of reaching the desired position. During the cruising phase, the main logic is to make all the vertical forces cancel each other, in other words, the resultant force in vertical direction is made to go to zero. Hence the thrust input is given in such a way that they are equal to the G-forces on the body, that is, $m * g$. Where m is the mass of the quadcopter and g is the acceleration due to gravity. This is followed by a yaw angle in the case where the quadcopter is required to go sideways or in a forward motion (slight pitch down) to provide a resultant force in the forward direction. Finally, the decent employs the logic of providing lesser thrust inputs compared to the force due to gravity which causes the body to slowly descend. This input may also be accompanied by a yaw or pitch angle input based on the angle of decent requirement (Svacha et al, 2017). The above explained logic is given by the below mentioned algorithm.

motor. As the name suggests, the position controller controls the position and adjusts the position of the quadcopter. Hence the control input given by this is represented by u_1 which is the summation of all the forces produced by all the motors. It also takes the input from the rigid body dynamics in order to compute the total amount of relevant thrust that is needed. Hence this control is given to the motor to provide an appropriate thrust in order for the motors to thrust up the quadcopter to the next position. Position controller also sends the input to the attitude controller which is responsible for controlling the attitude or adjusting the attitude or heading of the quadcopter. This input is represented as R desired and is responsible for performing any attitude adjustments in order to reach the next position at the proper heading. This is important to perform as it keeps the quadcopter stabilized. The attitude controller gives the second set of inputs that is u_2 . It sends the input in terms of moments and torques to the motor in order to stabilise the motion of the quadcopter from the current position to the next position. In plane terms, it makes the motion of the quadcopter smooth without letting it wobble. To achieve this it also uses the input from the rigid body dynamics fed to the program (Guerrero-Bonilla et al, 2017).

The above algorithm is also explained mathematically as given below:

Defining the feedback as an error calculator:

$$e_i = (r_i - r_{iT}) \quad (19)$$

It is desirable that this error, e_i goes exponentially to zero. In order to achieve that, we require,

$$(\ddot{r}_i^{des} - \ddot{r}_i, \dot{r}_i) + k_{d,i}(r_i - r_{iT}) + k_{p,i}(r_i - r_{iT}) = 0 \quad (20)$$

r_{iT} and \dot{r}_{iT} (its time derivative) are given by the trajectory generator r_i and \dot{r}_i is given by the state estimation system. Therefore, \ddot{r}_i^{des} is given by:

$$\ddot{r}_i^{des} = \ddot{r}_{iT} - k_{d,i}(\dot{r}_i - \dot{r}_{iT}) - k_{p,i}(r_i - r_{iT}) \quad (21)$$

Firstly, a desired trajectory or the path that the quadcopter has to take is given as an input to the program. This is used as an input to the position controller which sends the thrusting signals to the

Figure 2: Controller algorithm

1.4 Linearization

Since the control law used is limited to linear systems so is the simulation hence there is a need for linearization. The obtained equation 21 is non-linear in nature and hence has to be linearized. This can be achieved by making expendable assumptions in order to obtain a linear equation that the controller and hence the simulation is able to handle to produce the result. The process of linearization is generally carried out around an equilibrium point. If the input is fixed, then the system renders the solution of the algebraic system. Mathematically, linearization or linear approximation of a function or a system is finding the first order Taylor expansion around the selected point. Linearization is also performed to assess the stability of a point, locally. When this stability is achieved all through the points then the system can be concluded as stable. In this case linearization is performed to obtain a solution to the algebraic system. Since the current system is non-linear the solution is hard to obtain as the trigonometric function are not related to any other in any elementary way. Hence it becomes crucial to linearize. This is achieved through simplified model of small oscillations, where sine functions are approximated with its arguments and cosine functions are approximated with its unity. For this approximation to be valid a small region or an argument is chosen. Linearizing \ddot{r}_i^{des} in order to control the attitude of the quadcopter (Salih et al, 2010).

$$\ddot{r}_i^{des} = \ddot{r}_{i,T} - k_{d,i}(\dot{r}_i - \dot{r}_{i,T}) - k_{p,i}(r_i - r_{i,T}) \quad (21)$$

$$\ddot{r}_1^{des} = g(\theta^{des} \cos \psi_T + \phi^{des} \sin \psi_T) \quad (22)$$

$$\ddot{r}_2^{des} = g(\theta^{des} \sin \psi_T - \phi^{des} \cos \psi_T) \quad (23)$$

$$\ddot{r}_3^{des} = \frac{1}{m} u_1 - g \quad (24)$$

Solving equation 22 and equation 23 for θ^{des} and ϕ^{des} can be calculated. Extending the process of linearization to u_2 , second input,

$$I \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\phi} \\ \ddot{\theta} \\ \ddot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = u_2 \quad (25)$$

Using PD controller (Luukkonen, 2011)

$$u_2 = I \begin{bmatrix} -k_{p,\phi}(\phi - \phi^{des}) & -k_{d,\phi}(p - p^{des}) \\ -k_{p,\theta}(\theta - \theta^{des}) & -k_{d,\theta}(q - q^{des}) \\ -k_{p,\psi}(\psi - \psi^{des}) & -k_{d,\psi}(r - r^{des}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

2. NUMERICAL MODEL

2.1 MATLAB model

The MATLAB model is a mathematical model for the numerical analysis or simulation. The entire numerical analysis is divided into two parts. Firstly, the high-level control system analysis and secondly the low-level control system analysis. The high-level control system comprises of the quadcopter simulation, path planning and trajectory generation and design and simulation of the controller which controls the entire simulation. The low-level control system comprises of the battery modelling, motor selection and motor modelling, load analysis and load modelling and finally SOC estimation and state of health monitoring.

In this study the high-level control system is analysed and modelled using MATLAB and low-level control system is analysed and modelled using SIMULINK.

The MATLAB model aims at modelling the quadcopter with its system parameters and to embed the controller capable of efficiently controlling the quadcopter. This section also deals with the trajectory generation based on the desired waypoints taken as input.

Firstly, it is important to initialise the state vectors of the system. They specify the position and velocity of the quadcopter hence it is important to initialise them. Initially the quadcopter is in the origin, that is, it starts to fly from the origin hence the initial position is set to zero. Since it is not

flying and is stagnant at (0,0,0) the quadcopter's velocity or angular velocity (ω) is set as zero. Since these two quantities are dependent on time they need to get updated at a specified time. For these state vectors to get updated accurately at each time step it is vital to initialise the time variable. This is generally done according to the time of start. As the quadcopter is assumed to start flying at zero seconds the initial time is set to zero. The initial acceleration of the quadcopter is also set to zero as it is not moving. The state vectors are to be updated and this can be done for every time step. For this the time step has to be defined and initialised accordingly. Based on an approximation of the total time taken for the entire flight of the quadcopter starting from climbing till decent the total time taken can be assumed. This assumption will also require the velocity with which the quadcopter is flying and the waypoints which it is going to pass through. Based on all this information an approximation of the total amount of time taken to complete the trajectory is found to be 220 seconds (approximately). This time also complies with the battery model as it is important for the battery to continue to power the motors of the quadcopter for the entirety of the flight. This in other words mean that there is a positive SOC and state of health of the battery which is later explained in the next sub-chapter on SIMULINK model.

Based on this assumption the time step is set to 0.01 seconds. The image of the graphic user interface is captured for every 0.05 seconds. Hence, for every 0.01 seconds the state vectors get updated based on their attitude command for the next position, based on their current position and on the velocity acquired (due to acceleration). The initial yaw angle of the quadcopter is also set to zero. This gets updated based on the attitude control received from the controller. Along with the state vectors certain co-efficient such as co-efficient of thrust and co-efficient of drag are also initialised. Co-efficient of thrust, b , is found to be $9.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{N/m}^2$ and co-efficient of drag, d , is found to be $1.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{N/m}^2$. These values are obtained experimentally using the test fly data.

After initialisation of the state vector the system model can be defined. The entire control system functions and analysis can be mathematically

expressed. This mathematical modelling is also known as system modelling. The system model talks about the control inputs and their dependencies on other variables. In this case there are two main control inputs which is sent from the controllers. As there is a need to control the position and decide the heading or the attitude of the quadcopter, they form the two main control inputs. These two system parameters are enough to stabilize the quadcopter if controlled properly. The position controller is represented by u_1 and the attitude controller is represented by u_2 . Both these inputs are passed on to the motor for proper control of the quadcopter u_1 is given by the below expressions:

$$u_1 = \sum_{i=1}^4 F_i \quad \text{expressed in terms of force or thrust.}$$

$$u_1 = m * \ddot{r}_3^{des} + g \quad \text{expressed in terms of acceleration.}$$

u_2 is given by the below expression

$$u_2 = I * \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p} \\ \dot{q} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{expressed in terms of moment of inertia and state vectors.}$$

$$u_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & l & 0 & -l \\ -l & 0 & l & 0 \\ \gamma & -\gamma & \gamma & -\gamma \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} F_1 \\ F_2 \\ F_3 \\ F_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{expressed in terms of force or thrust.}$$

These system model parameters are to be updated at each time step similar to the state vectors. These parameters depend on the equations of motion of the quadcopter. (Equation of quadcopter is explained in chapter 2). After each time step, each varying parameter of the equations of motion are to be modified or updated. As the control inputs depend on the equations of motion directly as they get updated u_1 and u_2 will also get updated after each time step.

2.1.1 System parameters of the quadcopter

While modelling the quadcopter model in the simulation it is vital to include the parameter of the quadcopter. The same has been modelled as given below:

Mass of the quadcopter is noted to be 1.5Kg

Acceleration due to gravity, $g=9.81\text{m/s}^2$

$$\text{Moment of inertia, } I = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0035 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0035 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.0035 \end{bmatrix} \text{m}^2$$

This value of the inertial tensor is calculated experimentally which is explained in the second chapter under mathematical modelling of the system.

The length of the arms of the quadcopter is noted as, $L = 0.225\text{m}$

It is also necessary to model the limits of the quadcopter (Fernando et al, 2013). This ensures that the quadcopter is not pushed beyond its limit even in the simulation. Although the quadcopter is expected to perform some extreme manoeuvres it cannot be pushed beyond a certain limit without damaging or compromising its structural integrity. Hence the limit is set in the simulation so that the simulation never exceeds these limits. The main parameters to consider for the limits are angle of yaw and thrusting force. The limits of the quadcopter is as given below:

Maximum angle of yaw is 40radians

Minimum angle of yaw is 0radians

Maximum thrusting force is 36.7875N

Minimum thrusting force is 0.73575N

The maximum thrusting force is calculated as 2.5mg and the minimum thrusting force is calculated as 0.05mg

The mass of the quadcopter includes the four motors, mount and the battery pack. These parameters are vital while updating the control inputs. They also play a vital role in keeping the quadcopter within its limits especially during climb or decent or during hovering.

3.2.3. Logic of Trajectory generation

The trajectory generation section of the code talks about the algorithm where the trajectory is generated for the quadcopter. Although the waypoints which the quadcopter has to follow is given as an input to the controller, an algorithm has to be created to impart the intelligence to follow the waypoints being input. The logic used to achieve the following of the trajectory covering all the waypoints should be similar to the quadcopter following in the real-world scenario. The waypoints given as an input in this study forms a series of steps before the quadcopter lands on the ground. The first series of steps checks the ability to do hard climbs thus confirming the copter's lifting or thrusting abilities. The second series of steps checks the ability to do hard descents thus confirming the copter's descending capabilities. The input trajectory is as shown in figure 3 below:

WP	lon	lat	alt
1	51.5516778	-3.3752871	0
2	51.5516778	-3.3752871	40
3	51.55306	-3.373661	40
4	51.55306	-3.373661	60
5	51.5544742	-3.3721161	60
6	51.5544742	-3.3721161	80
7	51.5566356	-3.3695412	80
8	51.5566356	-3.3695412	60
9	51.5576495	-3.3683395	60
10	51.5576495	-3.3683395	40
11	51.5587167	-3.367095	40
12	51.5587167	-3.367095	0

Figure 3: Trajectory of quadcopter from experiment

It is clear from the figure above that there are fourteen waypoints starting from lifting up till landing back on ground. The logic used in the generation of the trajectory is that the quadcopter comes to a full stop at the beginning of each waypoint. This is done so that the quadcopter does not exceed the waypoint given. This makes sure that the copter comes to a full stop and not undershoot or overshoot the mark. Although the copter never fully comes to a stop before each waypoint in the real-world scenario as it would be a huge burden on the battery and the motor if the copter comes to a full stop at each and every waypoint and then start again at full thrust to lift up immediately. As for the case of simulation, to visualise the following of the entire trajectory it

becomes necessary to stop at each waypoint for a second in order to not lose any thrust. A novel algorithm is devised to set the velocity to zero at each waypoint. The total time taken is divided into eleven steps as the trajectory consists of eleven paths. The time differential is set to 0.01 for the delay. The position is given as an input, velocity and acceleration is set accordingly.

If time is greater than zero and time is lesser than $tol_time / 11$ then,

The position is set to the next waypoint and velocity is set to accordingly.

If time is equal to $tol_time / 11$ then velocity is set to zero.

This algorithm continues for the next waypoint as follows:

If time is greater than $tol_time / 11$ and time is lesser than $2 * tol_time / 11$ then,

The position is set to the next waypoint and velocity is set to accordingly.

If time is equal to $2 * tol_time / 11$ then velocity is set to zero.

And this goes on till the end.

3.3. SIMULINK model

The SIMULINK model talks about the low-level control system. The low-level control system talks about the battery model and the motor model. It also talks about the loading parameters according to the loading conditions in modelled in the high-level control algorithm. It uses a step loading model as the loading is not constant throughout the flight and is different during different conditions of flight like, climb, hover and decent. The model is designed to estimate SOC and display it as an output. It also displays the motor parameters like, torque, armature current and motor speed.

3.3.3. Battery Modelling

The type of battery used in this study is Lithium based battery. The Li-ion or lithium-based batteries are not most commonly used in battery modelling. Some of the factors favouring the selection include higher energy capacity, lighter package, less state of discharge and optimal temperature performance curve. This study uses lithium composition as it is environmentally friendly. Even after its complete usage it's still environmentally friendly as most of the parts of the battery can be recycled. This enhances the arm of clean and electric propulsion system development. This study can also be extended towards electric propulsion of aircraft using a bigger battery pack or a battery with a better capacity. Electric propulsion is the future with electric motors and their controller being able to achieve an efficient performance of almost 90%. Hence this study becomes vital and essential to prove the model. It also reduces the carbon dioxide emission hence it is important to model the battery accurately as it is a greener form of energy. The chemical process of charging and discharging of lithium ion batteries is given by the below equation (Haizhou, 2017).

In this study the modelled battery is used to power four motors which is sued to propel the quadcopter weighing two kilograms.

Figure 4: DP equivalent circuit model

The figure shown above is the equivalent circuit for the battery model developed. Depending on the characteristics of the battery and its composition the resistor and capacitor branch will be one or more (He et al, 2011). Since, one resistor and capacitor branch serve the purpose of many

industrial applications, such a model has been adopted in this study (Zhang et al, 2017). The credibility of the model can be confirmed by running experimental tests on the charging and discharging of the battery. Their charging and discharging gives data that can be used to understand the battery performance. Battery performance also depends on the temperature at which the battery is subjected to run. Based on the temperature the performance varies hence, it is vital to understand the dependency of the particular battery on temperature and its relation to the performance. Based on the experimental data the SOC and state of discharge will differ based on the temperature at which the battery is being tested. This is vital to the study as it sheds more light on how the battery behaves in terms of SOC with respect to working temperature of the battery. Hence SOC and state of discharge are both constantly measured at each temperature to accurately model the battery and validate its SOC and state of discharge. The effects of aging are not taken into account in this study and hence not checked for even in the experiment.

In this study the temperature of the inner cell is assumed to be steady and uniform, hence an average temperature is assumed for the inner cell. This temperature is given by the below equation 28 (Hurria et al, 2012).

$$C_T \cdot \frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{T - T_a}{R_T} + P_s \quad (28)$$

Where,

C_T is the capacitance as a function of temperature, of the inner cell

T is temperature to which the battery is subjected or at which the battery is working

T_a is temperature of the inner cell

R_T is the resistance as a function of temperature, of the inner cell

Applying Laplace transform to the above equation:

$$T(s) = \frac{P_s R_T + T_a}{1 + R_T C_T s} \quad (29)$$

Based on the temperature data calculated, the battery model is developed and hence the performance curve of the battery is thereby developed. The effect of aging is ignored in this study for the ease of computational and calculation purposes.

SOC estimation

The main study of modelling and analysis of the battery model is to analyse or be capable of estimating the SOC of the battery. This is vital since it gives a measure of the amount of charge left in the battery or the amount of charge being consumed. SOC of a battery is defined as a ratio of battery's current capacity ($Q(t)$) to nominal capacity (Q_n). Nominal capacity represents the maximum amount of charge that the battery can store. Based in the above definition SOC can be defined as given below: (Li et al, 2016)

$$SOC(t) = \frac{Q(t)}{Q_n} \quad (30)$$

The importance of SOC estimation can also be stressed due to other reasons such as precise accountability of proper charge estimation at all given operating conditions of the vehicle and aging effects of the cell. In addition to this the high temperature effect can also vary the estimated SOC of the battery, broad SOC ranges of operation and the type of load being applied to the system like strenuous loading of the system may accelerate the aging process of the cell and affect SOC estimation.

As the analysis continues the error accumulates with time. This error accumulated can be rectified by calibrating the program once again accordingly, but this also means that by adopting this method the program would demand periodic recalibrations according to the errors accumulated. Hence to avoid this extra step, an alternative method, Kalman Filter is used to estimate the SOC of the battery. Since the battery pack is derived from the MATLAB library and it uses a pre-defined method to measure the SOC and the state of health of the battery the same has been explained below under Kalman Filter section.

Temperature effects of a Li-ion battery

Generally the temperature effects are due to the chemical reactions taking place in the batteries and also depends on the type of materials used in the battery. The rate of chemical reaction and the reaction of the temperature follows the trend of Arrhenius equation. Hence the temperature changes can lead to change in electrochemical reaction rate in Li-ion batteries. Changes or variations in the chemical reactions due to the temperature changes can also lead to changes in the ionic conductivities of electrolytes and electrodes.

3.3.4. Motor Model

A DC motor belongs to the class of rotary electrical machines that converts direct current into mechanical energy. Since DC motors can run on the existing direct current electrical energy source, they were the first forms of motor to be widely used across the world. The speed of a DC motor can be changed by either changing the variable supply voltage or by changing the strength of the current flowing through its field windings. A small DC motor is widely being used to run many numerous small appliances or toys etc. But a larger DC motor is nowadays being used to propel an electric vehicle, hoists, elevators, rolling mills etc.

Any DC motor is an electromagnetic motor as it has a set of stationary magnets in the stator and an armature. The armature has one or more insulated wires wound around them. These wires are wrapped around a soft iron core and it concentrates all the magnetic field. The wires are connected to the commutator which allows the coils to be energized and thus rotates (Luukkonen, 2011).

The DC motor are of two main types:

1. Brushed DC motor
2. Brushless DC motor

In this study, a brushless DC motor has been used. Hence a brushless DC motor is discussing in detail

and a brief overview of the workings of a brushed DC motor is explained as a comparison.

A typical DC motor has a permanent magnet on the outside and an armature on the inside. Since the permanent magnet is stationary it's called as the stator and as the armature rotates due to magnetic flux it's called as the rotor. In a brushed DC motor, the brushes come in contact with the electrodes in motion and create a magnetic flux causing rotation. They also flip the polarity thus keeping the rotation going. Certain disadvantages of a brushed DC motor are as follows

1. Brushes may wear out
2. May cause sparks as it makes or breaks connections
3. Limit the speed
4. Difficult to cool off.

Due to the above stated disadvantages a brushless motor is used in this study. In a brushless motor, the arrangement of the motor parts is reversed, and the brushes are ruled out (Matsui and Shigyo, 1992). The permanent magnets are put on the rotor and the electromagnets on the stator. A computer system is connected to energize the electromagnets as rotor rotates. Hence there is no need for a brush. Some of the advantages are: (Matsui and Shigyo, 1992)

1. Control the speed
2. Brushless hence no friction losses hence more efficient
3. No sparks
4. No wearing or tearing

Figure 5: DC Motor

Physical parameters of the DC motor are as given below:

Armature Voltage	240V
Field Voltage	300V
Power	5HP – 20HP
Speed	0–1750 rpm
Total Inertia	0.08321 km ²
Motor Viscous friction constant	0.004Nm.s
EMF constant	0.01 V/rad/s
Motor torque constant	6.01Nm/A
Resistance	0.4 Ω
Inductance	27 H

Table 2: DC motor Parameters

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \\ i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{b}{J} & \frac{K}{J} \\ \frac{K}{L} & -\frac{R}{L} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \\ i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{L} \end{bmatrix} V \quad (38)$$

$$y = [1 \quad 0] \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \\ i \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

System model of the DC motor

Since torque produced by a DC motor is proportional to its armature current in a DC motor as the below equation is arrived (Luukkonen, 2011).

$$T = k_t i$$

Back emf e is given by

$$e = k_e \dot{\theta}$$

$$k_t = k_e = k$$

According to Newton's 2nd law and Kirchoff's voltage law,

$$J\ddot{\theta} + b\dot{\theta} = ki \quad (33)$$

$$L \frac{di}{dt} + Ri = V - k\dot{\theta} \quad (34)$$

Applying Laplace transform

$$s(Ts + b) \theta(s) = KI(s) \quad (35)$$

$$(Ls + R) I(s) = V(s) - k_s \theta(s) \quad (36)$$

$$P(s) = \frac{\dot{\theta}(s)}{V(s)} \quad (37)$$

$$= \frac{K}{(Js + b)(Ls + R) + k^2} \left(\frac{\frac{rad}{s}}{V} \right)$$

Representing the above model in state space representation:

Current/conductor is given by $I_c = I_a \cdot A$

Force / conductor is given by $f_c = \frac{BLI_a}{A}$

Torque $T_c = f_c \cdot r = \frac{BLI_a \cdot r}{A}$

Therefore, $T_c = \frac{\phi P I_a}{2\pi A}$

Hence the total torque is given by $T_g = \frac{Pz\phi I_a}{2\pi A}$

$$T_g = k_a \phi I_a \quad (38)$$

$$k_a = \frac{PZ}{2\pi A} \quad (39)$$

Although the DC motor modelling is part of the low-level control system this has to be linked with the high-level control system. This is done so that the entire control system is as on and is coordinated between one another. To ensure this the loading of the quadcopter is given as the input of the motor model as well. In other words, the model is the entity lifting the copter hence it is the one to bear the loads. This load input that is given to the motor prompts the battery to supply power accordingly. Thus, every entity of both high and low-level control systems is interconnected. As the loading is not constant a step input of loads has to be given to the motor. Each input either corresponds to climbing or hovering or descending phase and hence have variable loading. According to the load accepted the motor demands for an appropriate power to be supplied. The parameter that is of interest is the speed of the motor and the armature current. These parameters are used to assess the performance of the motor. Hence a bus is used where both the parameters are fed and then displayed real time. The graph showing these data is given ad discussed in the Results section under SIMULINK subchapter.

3.3.5. Variable load modelling

The quadcopter is subjected to a varying load. As the quadcopter is not hovering all through its flight path and is actually performing certain climbing and descending manoeuvres. Due to these manoeuvres the quadcopter will not be undergoing the same load throughout the flight. The copter weighs 1.5 Kg including all the accessories, battery and the frame. The motors produce a thrust which is responsible for carrying the quadcopter upwards. Firstly the quadcopter has to be tested if it is capable of hovering and also to check the controller if it is capable of controlling by sending proper motor signals. For the quadcopter to hover, the two vertical forces must cancel each other out. The motor produces the upward force and the gravity produces the downward force. The downward force in their case is 1.5 G hence the motor has to produce the same amount of upward thrust. This will then cancel each other and let the copter hover in mid air. The forces are taken from the MATLAB simulation and this is then given as an input to the SIMULINK simulation. This input is used to model the variable loading to the motor and thus to the battery.

Firstly, 14.8 N is given as an input for the first 10 seconds during which it hovers before it starts climbing. Later another 14.8 N that is 1.5 G is added to the existing thrust. This ensures that the quadcopter lifts up as it climbs. This is done for another 10 seconds. By this time the copter would have reached a certain base height from where it starts the stepping up manoeuvre. To achieve this step up manoeuvre, a series of recursive +5 N and -5 N or +0.5 G and -0.5 G forces are given. The +0.5 G is for the accelerating part and the -.5 G is for the decelerating part of the step. Once the maximum height is reached then the quadcopter starts descending. The descent is also done as a step-down manoeuvre. For this again a +0.5 G and -0.5 G forces are given for accelerating and decelerating parts of the step respectively. After reaching back the base height a -1.5 G force is supplied to the motors in order to let the quadcopter touch the ground and land softly. From the above explanation it is clear that the loads are

carriable based on the stage and the manoeuvre that the copter is about to perform. Hence a variable load model is done and is combined in a summation block and supplied to the DC motor module. The instantaneous load being transformed is displayed using a scope for the ease of understandability.

3.4. Control law used

The designed controller is intended to control the motion of an unmanned quadcopter. With the specific trajectory given as an input the quadcopter is expected to follow the trajectory without any problems and within the desired time frame in order to conserve the battery power. This section of paper will enunciate about how the controller is designed to follow the specified trajectory and how the copter is being controlled in order to keep its stability throughout its flight. It also sheds light on how the controller was capable of generating the trajectory and the path using the waypoints that were given as an input. It also explains about yawing controls which is vital in order to make any kind of forward, upward, downward or backward motions. It becomes extremely essential in times of banking left or right, but this study is limited to horizontal and vertical motions without any hard bank angles.

Controller Description

This section shares details on keeping the yaw rate of the vehicle to a zero. This is done so that the quadcopter is not going to turn left or right or tilt on any one side as it is expected to move in a straight path. A proportional and derivative controller (PD controller) is applied in order to arrive at the command for the acceleration of the quadcopter. This acceleration term (\ddot{r}_i^{des}) is given by the below equation:

$$\ddot{r}_i^{des} = \ddot{r}_{i,T} + k_{d,i}(\dot{r}_{i,T} - \dot{r}_i) + k_{p,i}(r_{i,T} - r_i) \quad (42)$$

Where the terms $\ddot{r}_{i,T}$, \dot{r}_i and $r_{i,T}$ are the desired acceleration, velocity and position terms of the trajectory desired. Thrust control given to the quadcopter is given by the below equation:

$$u_1 = mg + \ddot{r}_3^{des} \quad (43)$$

The commands for roll and pitch angles are obtained by the following equations.

$$\phi^{des} = \frac{1}{g} (\ddot{r}_1^{des} \sin\psi_T - \ddot{r}_2^{des} \cos\psi_T) \quad (44)$$

$$\theta^{des} = \frac{1}{g} (\ddot{r}_1^{des} \cos\psi_T - \ddot{r}_2^{des} \sin\psi_T) \quad (45)$$

$$\psi^{des} = \psi_T \quad (46)$$

The PD control is then applied in order to control the attitude of the quadcopter. The attitude control is represented by the term u_2 and is given by

$$u_2 = I \begin{bmatrix} k_{p,\phi}(\phi^{des} - \phi) + k_{d,\phi}(p^{des} - p) \\ k_{p,\theta}(\theta^{des} - \theta) + k_{d,\theta}(q^{des} - q) \\ k_{p,\psi}(\psi^{des} - \psi) + k_{p,\psi}(r^{des} - r) \end{bmatrix} \quad (47)$$

Where,

p , q and r are the angular velocities

p^{des} , q^{des} and r^{des} are the desired angular velocities

p^{des} and q^{des} are set for zero

r^{des} is set to ψ_T

Including all the controller commands that are explained above, the controller demands for gains to be defined in addition to that. The gains help reduce the errors and prevent error accumulation. With every feedback that the controller gets the gains try and reduce the error and get the command back on track. The gains are set as given below:

$k_{p,1} = 5$	$k_{d,1} = 5$	$k_{p,\phi} = 3000$	$k_{d,\phi} = 300$
$k_{p,2} = 5$	$k_{d,2} = 5$	$k_{p,\theta} = 3000$	$k_{d,\theta} = 300$
$k_{p,3} = 2$	$k_{d,3} = 10$	$k_{p,\psi} = 3000$	$k_{d,\psi} = 300$

Table 3: Defining gains for the controller

It is clear from the above definition that the gain commands on the z-axis is greater than the gain commands on the other two axes. This is defined in such a way that the excess gain can compensate for the gravitational force.

Trajectory Generation

The study has been conducted by adopting a third order minimum acceleration trajectory and seventh order minimum snap trajectory. According to waypoints that are given to the controller the trajectory or the path is generated for the quadcopter to take. The logic used in order to make the quadcopter follow the set (desired) path is explained in this section.

Speed profile

This section talks about the speed that is set for the quadcopter at which it can fly during its flight. For this the waypoints are taken as an input. Based on the input waypoints in the path, the approximate time to complete the entire flight is calculated. Once the total time is known then the whole path is split into different sections. Based on the total numbers of sections obtained the total time is then divided by the total number of sections. In this study based on the desired speed at which the quadcopter is expected to fly and some initial test data the speed constant is set to 0.5. Hence the total time of flight of the copter is divided by the predefined speed constant of 0.5. This then distributes the total time to each segment based on the square root of each segment's path length. This logic is used so that the quadcopter goes faster along the longer segment while it flies relatively slower along the short segment. This type of speed profiling is proved to be safe in the MATLAB simulation and during real time testing.

Minimum Acceleration Trajectory

The most vital part is the trajectory generation and the most common logic widely used is the minimum acceleration trajectory. It comprises of third order polynomials for each segment and is robust enough to achieve a balance between safety, speed and preservation of computational economy.

The algorithm works with certain necessary constraints based on the number of segments present. For example if there are n segments then $4*n$ constraints are necessary to solve the third order polynomial (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011)

The four constraints from starting point to the end point are as follows:

$$x_s(t = 0) = P_s$$

$$x_e(t = T) = P_e$$

$$\dot{x}_s(t = 0) = 0$$

$$\dot{x}_e(t = T) = 0$$

$4*(n-1)$ constraints for other n-1 waypoints:

$$x_i(t_i) = x_{i-1}(t_i) = P_i$$

$$\dot{x}_i(t_i) = \dot{x}_{i-1}(t_i)$$

$$\ddot{x}_i(t_i) = \ddot{x}_{i-1}(t_i)$$

To fulfil the conditions of continuity, the velocity and position of adjacent trajectories at any waypoint must be equal that is acceleration = 0. With enough number of constraints the trajectories in x-coordinate axis can be obtained by performing matrix computation $x=A^{-1}.b$ in MATLAB. Similarly, the trajectories in y and z coordinate systems can also be obtained

Minimum Snap Trajectory

The minimum snap trajectory makes use of a seventh order polynomial equation for each segment. If there are n segments in the whole flight path, then $8*n$ constraints are necessary to solve the seventh order polynomial for the trajectory. Eight constraints for the start point and the end point: (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011)

$$x_s(t = 0) = P_s ; \quad x_e(t = T) = P_e$$

$$\dot{x}_s(t = 0) = 0 ; \quad \dot{x}_e(t = T) = 0$$

$$\ddot{x}_s(t = 0) = 0 ; \quad \ddot{x}_e(t = T) = 0$$

$$\ddot{\ddot{x}}_s(t = 0) = 0 ; \quad \ddot{\ddot{x}}_e(t = T) = 0$$

This logic takes into account both continuity at waypoints and zero at waypoints.

Continuity at waypoints: $8*(n-1)$ constraints for other n-1 waypoints:

$$x_i(t_i) = x_{i-1}(t_i) = P_i$$

$$\dot{x}_i(t_i) = \dot{x}_{i-1}(t_i)$$

$$\ddot{x}_i(t_i) = \ddot{x}_{i-1}(t_i)$$

$$\ddot{\ddot{x}}_i(t_i) = \ddot{\ddot{x}}_{i-1}(t_i)$$

$$x_i^{(4)}(t_i) = x_{i-1}^{(4)}(t_i)$$

$$x_i^{(5)}(t_i) = x_{i-1}^{(5)}(t_i)$$

$$x_i^{(6)}(t_i) = x_{i-1}^{(6)}(t_i)$$

The position, velocity, jerk and acceleration of trajectories that are adjacent must be equal i.e. snap=0.

Zero at waypoints: $8*(n-1)$ constraints for n-1 waypoints

$$x_i(t_i) = x_{i-1}(t_i) = P_i$$

$$\dot{x}_i(t_i) = 0$$

$$\dot{x}_{i-1}(t_i) = 0$$

$$\ddot{x}_i(t_i) = 0$$

$$\ddot{x}_{i-1}(t_i) = 0$$

$$\ddot{\ddot{x}}_i(t_i) = 0$$

$$\ddot{\ddot{x}}_{i-1}(t_i) = 0$$

The position of two adjacent trajectories must be equal. Acceleration, velocity and jerk of two adjacent trajectories must be zero. With sufficient constraints, performing the matrix computation, $x=A^{-1}.b$ in MATLAB the desired trajectory in x and similar trajectories in y and z coordinate systems can be obtained (Mellinger and Kumar, 2011).

4. DATA ACQUISITION AND VALIDATION

Simulation is the best way to test the workings of a model. This way any errors encountered can be corrected by incurring least damages. At the same time the model that has been simulated has to be

tested for to confirm the results of the simulation. The done model used for the experimental set up is DJI F450. The specifications of the drone are as given below:

Diagonal wheelbase	450mm
Motor	Brushless DC Motor
ESC	30A ESC
Weight of the frame	282g
Weight range during t/o	800g-1600g
Weight of landing gear	17.5g on each arm
Propeller	10*3.8" ; 8*4.5"
Battery	Li-ion

Table 4: Quadcopter Specifications

The quadcopter is set up with a flight controller capable of auto piloting the entire system. It is also fitted with a GPS tracking device, gyroscope and a gopro camera. The GPS device comes with its own software. The desired waypoints can be given as an input to the controller of the quadcopter using its graphic user interface. This input is then given as an input to the GPS system. Based on the distance between the current and the next position the flight controller sends a command to the motors of the quadcopter. This control command is in terms of u_1 that is communicating thrust and u_2 that is controlling the torques and moments of the quadcopter. A desired velocity is set to the quadcopter. Using this velocity limit and the thrusting, moment and torque commands the electronic speed controller also known as ESC gives the signal to the motor which allows it to spin the exact amount to produce the desired effect. ESC also acts as a limiter for the speed at which the motor rotates. Before the quadcopter is allowed to perform extreme manoeuvres, it is first let to hover. This is done in order to check the perfect working of all systems such as motors, ESCs, etc., against the given command. While testing for the validity of the simulation there are two plausible approaches that can be taken. Once is to manually give the commands of the waypoints into the quadcopter system using a controller. An alternative option is to link the controller in the simulation with the software used in the quadcopter. This way the quadcopter becomes autonomous as the designed controller takes care of controlling the copter. In this study the quadcopter is tested for both the cases and has rendered the same result.

As the controller gives an input to the software on the copter, it sends a motor signal. This signal is computed based on equations of motion, control logic and system modelling. The ESC controls the speed of the copter according to the control law used in the simulation. The GPS relays the position of the copter real time to the controller in the form of a feedback system. This feedback is used as a check to see if the desired waypoint is reached or not. If not, the gain is used to send a correction signal to the motor and the process continues throughout the mission. The gopro camera is sued to capture images based on the application for which the copter is being used. Based on the controller signals the quadcopter was flown both manually and autonomously and the GPS software was used to either relay the data automatically to the controller or to a GUI. This data is plotted against time and compared against the simulation results. This is further discussed in the results section.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The above study confirms that the modelled quadcopter is robust enough for flight and to follow the trajectory generated. The results of graphs from the simulation shown below that the quadcopter is able to fly whilst the controller keeps it steady and stable.

Figure 6: Trajectory of quadcopter

The above figure shows the trajectory generated and the copter following the trajectory. Based on the waypoints given the model generates a trajectory and guides the quadcopter model to follow the specified path. The generated trajectory (desired trajectory) is given by a blue line and the trajectory that the copter follows is given by a red line. Since the copter follows the desired trajectory accurately the two lines merge.

Figure 7: X,Y and Z Position plot (3D)

Figures 7 show the position plots of the quadcopter Vs times. The vertical lines represent the lateral movement of the quadcopter maintaining the altitude and the horizontal lines in the plot shows the climb and decent phase of the quadcopter. From this graph the climb and the decent phases aren't evident hence the third plot, is plotted. It shows the entire trajectory followed by the quadcopter. Although the simulation (figure 6) shows a sharp edge, in real-world the quadcopter doesn't make a sharp turn during flight but makes a cured turn this is justified in the z-direction position plot as shown in figure 7. The y-direction position represents the fluctuations of the quadcopter during flight. It is evident from the plot that the quadcopter doesn't fluctuate much but tends towards left as it flies comparable to the experimental test data given by table 5. Any undesirable fluctuations are well within the acceptable range as shown in figure 7 and hence confirm the experimental data.

Figure 8: Velocity plot in all three directions

From figure 8 it is evident that the velocity in y-direction is almost zero and hence a 2D approximation for this simulation holds good. This is also due to the assumption that all aerodynamic forces (gust, etc) are neglected in y-direction. The 2D results for the same simulation are as given below.

Figure 9: 2D trajectory

Figure 9: 2D position plot

Figure 10: 2D velocity plot

The position and the velocity plots for 2D and 3D follow the same trend with the only difference in y-axis data. Hence it can be confirmed that the 2D simulation holds a good approximation to the 3D analysis in bring out the same results. It also confirms the assumption of neglecting y-data or approximating it to zero. The results from other quadcopter characteristics are the same irrespective of the simulation and they are as discussed below.

The quadcopter finishes its ToF at approximately the same time as the experiment. A comparison between the experimental and simulation data is show in the table below:

Table 5: Experimental Vs simulation results

EXPERIMENTAL TIME OF FLIGHT	SIMULATION TIME OF FLIGHT
237.5s	220s
Total Distance=10m	Total Distance=10m

Table 6: Experimental Vs Simulation thrust

	Experiment	Simulation
Max Thrust	34.3N	30N
Min Thrust	12.74N	13.72N
Weight of quadcopter	1300g	1500g (including battery+ESC+Wires)

From the above table 5 it is apparent that the error is 7.368% which is well within the acceptable error margin. Table 6 also shows that the thrust ranges of the simulation is within the thrust ranges of the experimental test data and that which the motors can produce.

Figure 11: angular velocity (squared) plot against time of each motor respectively

Figure 12: Thrust VS time plot

The above figure 11 and 12 show the plot of angular velocity of all the motors and overall thrust of the quadcopter respectively. It is clear from figure 8 that all the motors are providing equal thrusts at any given time. Hence all the motors are equally powered and modelled accurately. It is also evident from the two images that all the plots follow the same trend and the explanation for which is explained in the next section. The peak represents the acceleration and deceleration in a path. The first three peaks represent the climbing phase while the last three peaks represent the

descending phase. The horizontal lines represent hovering or moving forward with no lifting force.

Figure 13a: Battery and motor parameters vs time

The above image shows the results from the simulation from the SIMULINK on battery modelling. It shows the results of all the parameters from the battery and the motor model vs time. The speed plotted from the results of the simulation matches with the speed range of the DC motor. Speed range of the actual motor ranges between 0-3500rpm and the simulation ranges between 0-3300rpm, hence proves that the motor model is close to reality. The voltage values stay within 220V and hence complies with the actual values. The other parameters, Torque, Current and SoC is discussed in the next graph.

Figure 13b: Battery Parameters vs time

The above image shows the SOC estimation from vs time from the modelled battery. This shows that the battery sustains for 994s with extreme manoeuvres. Experimental test flights with extreme manoeuvres showed that the battery could

last for around 1070s, putting the error to 7.1%. Since the current study doesn't carry out any extreme manoeuvres, the battery can sufficiently power the quadcopter for its entire mission and still be left with some charge. Hence the modelled propulsion system is efficient in propelling the quadcopter. The variable load values are obtained from the flight data from simulation and fed into the motor model as torque. Due to climbing, hovering and decent the values aren't constant. Hence there is a variation in the torque plot. Armature current depends on loading conditions. It is evident from the above plot that current follows the same trend as that of torque. It dips when the loading reduces as the demand for current reduces.

Figure 14: Trajectory and SOC comparison

The above figure shows the trajectory and SOC of the battery comparison. The blue line represents the trajectory of the quadcopter and the red line shows the SOC of the battery. This figure is important as it shows the percentage of charge left in the battery at each corresponding point on the trajectory of the quadcopter. It gives a better understanding of the remaining charge and if the copter is able to complete the entire mission and return. A reserve of 30-50% charge is considered for extreme or complex manoeuvres. Thus making it a robust model and simulation of the same.

Figure 15: Torque loading against trajectory of the quadcopter

The above image shows the comparison between the trajectory of the quadcopter and the torque loading from the DC motor model. It is evident from the above figure that the torque loading is accurate as it goes to zero when the trajectory comes to a stop. Torque is the load applied on the motor which in return provides thrust to propel the quadcopter.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The trajectory generated and followed shows that the logic and the algorithm generated is accurate. This can be ascertained by the overlap of the blue (desired trajectory) and red (actual trajectory) lines. Comparing the experimental data and the generated trajectory it is clear that both are same and hence the model provides an accurate simulation. It is evident from the results section that the fluctuations in y-direction is within the acceptable range and hence it can be concluded that the feedback-controller is able to stably control the model. This confirms as a validation for the efficiency and the accuracy of the designed controller as the system is stable and follows the same path as that of the experimental trajectory obtained by the on-board GPS device. The battery modelled has proved to be sufficient to power the entire simulation and still be left with charge. Hence it can be concluded that the battery model

is efficient in serving the purpose. It is also evident from the modelling results that the battery can sustain up to 994s even during extreme loading conditions thus proving its robustness. This in turn proves that the load modelling acquired from MATLAB simulation and fed to the motor model is accurate in simulating the desired effect.

The model is designed to be modular so that any waypoints that is given, the controller will be able to generate an optimal trajectory as a function of time. The modelled battery and motor coupling are also efficient and modular. The DC motor model can be increased in power or number and so is the battery to simulate a bigger drone. It can also be reduced in power to propel a smaller drone such as crazyflie. In conclusion, by confirming the accuracies of all the three models and the controller designed, it is clear from the results section that the models are accurate and acceptable.

6.1. Future Works

There is a huge potential for the future works of the study. The prospects of which are as described below:

Extending the simulation to an electric aircraft

There has been a dire need to reduce the amount of greenhouse gas emission in order to keep the environment safe and clean and also conserve the fossil fuels. This can be achieved by extending the battery pack to more to suffice the load of the aircraft. The MATLAB model is modular and can accommodate an aircraft model and its weight⁶. By making these amends the same algorithm can simulate the flight of an electric aircraft.

Nonlinear and adaptive control

The controller used in the model is a PD controller which is linear in nature. This can be modified to an adaptive controller which can handle all the nonlinearities of the problem without making any assumptions or approximations⁵.

Neural-Network

Neural-Network is the latest technological development in the domain of control systems. This replaces the controller that was used and

works more intelligently. The initial data is given to model the NN system and any further testing only helps it to learn and develop based on nth data it has received². Hence is smarter than a controller although takes more time for it to test and train but is highly reliable.

Battery Management System

Kalman filter is used in the battery model to measure SOC in this study. An alternative means to measure SOC without a hassle would be to use a BMS system. In this all the outlet parameters of the battery like current and voltage are given as a feedback to the BMS¹. It then calculates the amount of current that was given out and hence the amount that is remaining. It measures SOC in the form of feedback signals and limits the usage of complex mathematical models¹.

7. REFERENCES

1. Cheng, K.W.E., Divakar, B.P., Wu, H., Ding, K. and Ho, H.F., 2010. Battery-management system (BMS) and SOC development for electrical vehicles. *IEEE transactions on vehicular technology*, 60(1), pp.76-88.
2. Chen, Y.W. and Chiu, W.Y., 2015, November. Optimal robot path planning system by using a neural network-based approach. In *2015 international automatic control conference (CACCS)* (pp. 85-90). IEEE.
3. Ceraolo, M., Lutzemberger, G. and Huria, T., 2011. *Experimentally determined models for high-power lithium batteries* (No. 2011-01-1365). SAE Technical Paper.
4. Das, S., Steager, E.B., Hsieh, M.A., Stebe, K.J. and Kumar, V., 2018. Experiments and open-loop control of multiple catalytic microrobots. *Journal of Micro-Bio Robotics*, 14(1-2), pp.25-34.
5. Dydek, Z.T., Annaswamy, A.M. and Lavretsky, E., 2012. Adaptive control of quadrotor UAVs: A design trade study with flight evaluations. *IEEE Transactions on control systems technology*, 21(4), pp.1400-1406.
6. Ehsani, M., Rahman, K.M. and Toliyat, H.A., 1997. Propulsion system design of electric and hybrid vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on industrial electronics*, 44(1), pp.19-27.
7. Fasano, G., Accardo, D., Moccia, A., Carbone, C., Ciniglio, U., Corrado, F. and Luongo, S., 2008. Multi-sensor-based fully autonomous non-cooperative collision avoidance system for unmanned air vehicles. *Journal of aerospace computing, information, and communication*, 5(10), pp.338-360.
8. Featherstone, R., 2014. *Rigid body dynamics algorithms*. Springer.
9. Fernando, H.C.T.E., De Silva, A.T.A., De Zoysa, M.D.C., Dilshan, K.A.D.C. and Munasinghe, S.R., 2013, December. Modelling, simulation and implementation of a quadrotor UAV. In *2013 IEEE 8th International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems* (pp. 207-212). IEEE.
10. Guerrero-Bonilla, L., Mohta, K., Bhattacharya, S. and Kumar, V., 2017, June. Flight trajectory tracking and recovery in presence of large disturbances. In *2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)* (pp. 1438-1446). IEEE.
11. Haizhou, Z., 2017. Modeling of Lithium-ion Battery for Charging/Discharging Characteristics Based on Circuit Model. *International Journal of Online Engineering*, 13(6).
12. He, H., Xiong, R. and Fan, J., 2011. Evaluation of lithium-ion battery equivalent circuit models for state of charge estimation by an experimental approach. *energies*, 4(4), pp.582-598.
13. Huria, T., Ceraolo, M., Gazzarri, J. and Jackey, R., 2012, March. High fidelity electrical model with thermal dependence for characterization and simulation of high-power lithium battery cells. In *2012 IEEE International Electric Vehicle Conference* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.

14. Kreciglowa, N., Karydis, K. and Kumar, V., 2017, June. Energy efficiency of trajectory generation methods for stop-and-go aerial robot navigation. In *2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)* (pp. 656-662). IEEE.
15. Li, Y., Wang, C. and Gong, J., 2016. A combination Kalman filter approach for State of Charge estimation of lithium-ion battery considering model uncertainty. *Energy*, 109, pp.933-946.
16. Luukkonen, T., 2011. Modelling and control of quadcopter. *Independent research project in applied mathematics, Espoo*, 22.
17. Matsui, N. and Shigyo, M., 1992. Brushless DC motor control without position and speed sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, 28(1), pp.120-127. (Matsui and Shigyo, 1992)
18. McDonald, D., 2012. Electric vehicle drive simulation with matlab/simulink. In *Proceedings of the 2012 North-Central Section Conference*.
19. Mellinger, D. and Kumar, V., 2011, May. Minimum snap trajectory generation and control for quadrotors. In *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation* (pp. 2520-2525). IEEE.
20. Ng, K.S., Huang, Y.F., Moo, C.S. and Hsieh, Y.C., 2009, October. An enhanced coulomb counting method for estimating state-of-charge and state-of-health of lead-acid batteries. In *INTELEC 2009-31st International Telecommunications Energy Conference* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
21. Salih, A.L., Moghavvemi, M., Mohamed, H.A. and Gaeid, K.S., 2010, May. Modelling and PID controller design for a quadrotor unmanned air vehicle. In *2010 IEEE International Conference on Automation, Quality and Testing, Robotics (AQTR)* (Vol. 1, pp. 1-5). IEEE
22. Svacha, J., Mohta, K. and Kumar, V., 2017, June. Improving quadrotor trajectory tracking by compensating for aerodynamic effects. In *2017 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)* (pp. 860-866). IEEE.
23. Watterson, M., Smith, T. and Kumar, V., 2016, October. Smooth trajectory generation on SE (3) for a free flying space robot. In *2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (pp. 5459-5466). IEEE.
24. Zhang, L., Peng, H., Ning, Z., Mu, Z. and Sun, C., 2017. Comparative research on RC equivalent circuit models for lithium-ion batteries of electric vehicles. *Applied Sciences*, 7(10), p.1002.

APPENDIX
